

1 **Role of the different copper species on the activity of** 2 **Cu/zeolite catalysts for SCR of NO_x with NH₃**

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12 13 14 **Abstract**

15
16 The SCR of NO_x with NH₃ has been studied by using different Cu zeolite
17 catalysts, prepared both with ZSM5 and BETA zeolite supports by ionic exchange or by
18 impregnation. The catalysts were characterized by ICP-AES, N₂ adsorption at -196 °C,
19 XRD, TEM, XPS and H₂-TPR. The catalysts characterization confirmed the presence of
20 different Cu(II) species on all catalyst (CuO and Cu(II) exchanged on tetrahedral and
21 octahedral positions of the zeolites framework). Clear evidences of Cu(I) or Cu(0)
22 species were not obtained. CuO was more abundant in high copper-content catalysts
23 and in ZSM5 catalysts, due to its lower ionic exchange capacity, while isolated Cu(II)
24 ions are more abundant in low copper-content catalysts and in BETA catalysts. It was
25 concluded that CuO catalyzes the oxidation of NO to NO₂, and this favors the reduction
26 of NO_x at lower temperature (the NH₃-NO₂ reaction is faster than the NH₃-NO reaction
27 because NO₂ is much more oxidizing than NO), whereas isolated Cu(II) ions maintain
28 high NO_x conversion at high temperatures.

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32 **Keywords:** SCR, NO_x removing, Cu-zeolite, Cu cluster

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42 **Graphical Abstract**

43 ● Exchange site

44

45 **1. Introduction**

46 It is well recognized that the use of diesel and lean burn engines decreases the
47 fuel consumption and thereby reduces the CO₂ emissions. However, conventional
48 three way catalysts (TWC) are not capable to reduce nitrogen oxides (NO_x) from diesel
49 engines due to the excess of oxygen in the exhaust. In the last decade, one of the main
50 approaches proposed for NO_x reduction in diesel exhausts has been the selective
51 catalytic reduction (SCR).

52 SCR was originally developed for stationary emission sources, mainly power
53 plants [1]. However, it soon turned out to be a promising technology for the NO_x
54 removal in automobile applications as well [2]. In 2005 it was introduced for commercial
55 heavy-duty vehicles in Europe, and more recently also for passenger cars. The NH₃-
56 SCR converter needs an external source of the selective reducing agent, e.g. urea.
57 The urea solution is injected in a controlled way into the exhaust line, where it is
58 thermally decomposed into NH₃ and CO₂. The ammonia then reacts selectively with
59 NO_x under lean (oxidising) conditions, giving N₂ as the final product [3]. Non-noble
60 metals like copper, iron and cerium supported on ZSM5 and BETA zeolite are among
61 the most active catalysts for the urea/NH₃-SCR process [4-7].

62 Cu(II) ion-exchanged ZSM5 (Cu-ZSM5) zeolites were first tested, showing high
63 NO decomposition rates and NO_x SCR activities [8]. More recently, Cu(II)-exchanged
64 beta zeolites (Cu-BETA) have shown a good activity for the NH₃-SCR of NO_x, but they
65 present better hydrothermal stability than similar ZSM5 catalysts [9]. Burch et al. [10]
66 identified the presence of Cu(I) species under reaction conditions, and proposed that
67 Cu(I) is the main active species for the reaction. Whatever, it is generally accepted that
68 both copper ions (Cu(II) and/or Cu(I)), which exist in the exchange sites of ZSM5, play
69 an important role in the reaction of NH₃-SCR. In the last decade, a lot of research has

70 been performed to obtain information about the nature of the copper active sites for this
71 process [11-15].

72 Nevertheless, there is still an open discussion concerning the chemical and
73 mechanistic aspects involved in SCR, mainly those related with the role of the different
74 copper species exchanged or placed on the zeolite. In our previous work [16], we have
75 analysed the NH₃-SCR catalytic performance of different ZSM5 and BETA supported
76 catalysts, varying the preparation method and copper content. We found that while
77 ZSM5 supported catalysts achieved better NO_x conversion in a low temperature range
78 (250-350 °C), BETA supported catalysts were active at higher temperature (350-450
79 °C). On the other hand, an increase in the copper content and the use of an
80 impregnation preparation method (vs. the ion exchange) allows achieving higher NO_x
81 conversion at lower temperatures but it decreases at intermediate and higher
82 temperatures.

83 The aim of this work is to understand the role of the different copper species on
84 the activity of Cu/zeolite catalysts in the NH₃-SCR process for NO_x removal in a wide
85 temperature range (140–500 °C). For characterization of the different Cu-zeolite
86 catalysts, which were prepared by both impregnation and ion-exchange methods, XPS,
87 H₂-TPR and TEM techniques have been used.

88

89 **2. Experimental**

90 *2.1. Catalysts preparation.*

91 The SCR catalysts consisted of copper-supported zeolites. Fresh zeolites were
92 supplied by Zeolyst International, namely CP414E (BETA, Si/Al=12.5) and CBV5524G
93 (ZSM5, Si/Al=25). The zeolites were first calcined at 550 °C for 4 h to obtain the acid
94 form. The catalysts were prepared by two different conventional procedures: ion

95 exchange (IE) and wetness impregnation (IM). Metal ion exchange was carried out by
96 dissolving the required amount of $\text{Cu}(\text{COOCH}_3)_2$ (Panreac, 98%) in water. Then, H-
97 ZSM5 or H-BETA was added to this solution (8 g/L) and it was stirred for 24 h at 65 °C.
98 The ion exchanged zeolites were then filtered, washed twice with deionized water,
99 dried overnight at 110 °C and calcined at 550 °C for 4 h.

100 On the other hand, the wetness impregnation method consisted of adding
101 slowly the required amount of the copper precursor dissolved in water (1.5 wt.%) at 40
102 °C and 3 mm Hg to 6 grams of H-beta or H-ZSM5, under continuous rotation until the
103 solvent was evaporated. The samples were dried overnight at 110 °C and calcined at
104 550 °C for 4 h.

105 All the catalysts were then pelletized, crushed and sieved to 0.3-0.5 mm.
106 Previous experiments carried out with different particle size catalysts revealed that
107 mass transfer limitations were not controlling the reaction kinetics for a particle size of
108 0.3-0.5 mm.

109 The most relevant details of the preparation procedure of copper-zeolite
110 catalysts, as well as the nomenclature used are summarized in Table 1. For each
111 support, BETA or ZSM5, four catalysts were prepared, three by ion exchange and one
112 by wetness impregnation. With regards to the ion exchange catalysts, increasing
113 copper concentration solutions (160, 320, 640 and 2000 ppm) were used in order to
114 obtain different copper loading on the zeolitic support.

115 TABLE 1

116

117

118 *2.2. Characterization techniques.*

119 *ICP-AES.* The actual amount of copper in the prepared catalysts was
120 determined by ICP-AES, after metal extraction from the solid samples with 1:2
121 HNO₃:HF mixture at 90 °C, which assures complete samples dissolving.

122 *N₂ adsorption.* The BET surface area of the zeolite samples were determined by
123 N₂ adsorption at -196 °C using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 equipment.

124 *XR Diffraction (XRD).* The crystalline structure of the copper modified zeolite
125 samples were analyzed by XRD (Philips PW1710 diffractometer). The samples were
126 finely ground and X-Ray diffractograms were recorded with copper K α radiation in
127 continuous scan mode from 5 to 80° of 2 θ with 0.02° per second sampling interval.
128 PANalytical X'pert HighScore specific software was used for data treatment. JCPDS
129 database was used to interpret the diffractograms.

130 *X Ray Photoelectronic Spectroscopy (XPS).* XPS characterization was carried
131 out in a VG-Microtech Multilab electron spectrometer using Mg-K α (1254.6 eV)
132 radiation source. To obtain the XPS spectra, the pressure of the analysis chamber was
133 maintained at $5 \cdot 10^{-10}$ mbar. The binding energy (BE) scale was adjusted by setting
134 the carbon 1s transition at 284.6 eV. The XPS measurements were performed in the
135 electron binding energy ranges corresponding to copper 2p, oxygen 1s, silicon 2p,
136 aluminum 2p and carbon 1s core excitations [17, 18].

137 *Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM).* A JOEL (JEM-2010) microscope was
138 used to obtain TEM images of the catalysts. Few droplets of an ultrasonically dispersed
139 suspension of each sample in ethanol were placed on a copper grid with lacey carbon
140 film and dried at ambient conditions for TEM characterizations. In order to obtain
141 particle size distribution of copper, around 200 copper particles were identified and
142 measured.

143 *Hydrogen Temperature Programmed Reduction (H₂-TPR)*. Reducibility of
144 copper catalysts was investigated by TPR using H₂. The samples were pretreated in 30
145 ml/min of 10% O₂/He mixture gas flow at 550 °C for 45 min and then cooled down to 30
146 °C and flushed out with helium for 60 min. Then the samples were heated from room
147 temperature to 600 °C with 10 °C/min ramp in a 60 ml/min of 5% H₂/Ar mixture gas
148 flow. The water formed during reduction with H₂ was trapped using a cold trap and the
149 hydrogen consumption was continuously monitored with a TCD detector.

150

151 2.3. SCR experiments.

152 The SCR experiments were performed in a down flow stainless steel reactor.
153 The reactor tube, with 1 g of 0.3-0.5 mm pelletized Cu-zeolite SCR catalyst inside, was
154 located into a 3-zone tube furnace. The temperature was measured by a thermocouple
155 at the top of the catalyst bed. The reaction temperature was varied from 100 to 500 °C
156 in steps of 40 °C. The composition of the feed gas mixture was 750 ppm NO, 750 ppm
157 NH₃ and 9.5% O₂ using Ar as the balance gas. Gases were fed via mass flow
158 controllers and the total flow rate was set at 3000 ml·min⁻¹, which corresponded to a
159 space velocity (GHSV) of 90,000 h⁻¹. The experimental set-up was designed to
160 minimize the gas phase oxidation of NO to NO₂, and therefore, the NO₂ concentration
161 in the gas fed is almost null. The NO, NO₂ NH₃ and N₂O concentrations at the reactor
162 exit were monitored every 40 °C, once the analysis has been stabilized for at least 10
163 min, by an online FTIR multigas analyzer (MKS 2030).

164 The NO (X_{NO}) and NH₃ (X_{NH3}) conversions were calculated as

$$165 \quad X_{NO} = \frac{F_{NO}^{in} - F_{NO_x}^{out}}{F_{NO}^{in}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$166 \quad X_{NH_3} = \frac{F_{NH_3}^{in} - F_{NH_3}^{out}}{F_{NH_3}^{in}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

167 and the N_2 (S_{N_2}), NO_2 (S_{NO_2}) and N_2O (S_{N_2O}) selectivities were calculated as

$$168 \quad S_{N_2} = \frac{2F_{N_2}^{out}}{F_{NH_3}^{in}X_{NH_3} + F_{NO}^{in}X_{NO}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$169 \quad S_{NO_2} = \frac{F_{NO_2}^{out}}{F_{NH_3}^{in}X_{NH_3} + F_{NO}^{in}X_{NO}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$170 \quad S_{N_2O} = \frac{2F_{N_2O}^{out}}{F_{NH_3}^{in}X_{NH_3} + F_{NO}^{in}X_{NO}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

171 where F_i represents the concentration of the “i” specie and the superscripts “in” and
172 “out” indicate that the gas concentration was measured at the inlet and the exit of the
173 reactor, respectively.

174

175 **3. Results and Discussion.**

176 *3.1 Analysis of the copper content and surface area of the catalysts.*

177 Figure 1 shows the copper loading of the different catalysts prepared by ionic
178 exchange with regard to the initial copper concentration on the water solutions used for
179 the exchange process. An auxiliary continuous line has been included which
180 represents the maximum copper loading that would be achieved if all copper available
181 in the water solutions were incorporated into the zeolites. Furthermore, two auxiliary
182 dot lines represent the maximum amount of copper that can be exchanged on each
183 zeolite. The Si/Al ratios and the corresponding molecular composition of the ZSM5 and
184 BETA zeolites (Table 1) predict these maxima amounts of copper are 2 and 5.6 wt. %,
185 respectively, considering that one Cu(II) cation needs two ionic exchange sites.

186

FIGURE 1

187 All data on Figure 1 lie below the concentration predicted by the auxiliary
188 continuous line corresponding to maximum copper loading, evidencing that there is

189 copper left in the water solutions after the exchange processes. The amount of copper
190 loaded on both zeolites increases with copper concentration in the water solution, and
191 as a general trend, the amount of copper loaded on the ZSM5 zeolite is lower to that
192 loaded on BETA zeolite (for similar exchange conditions). This is in agreement with the
193 Si/Al ratios and with the exchange capacity of each zeolite. The copper loading on the
194 BETA zeolite catalysts increases with the copper concentration on the water solution
195 until total consumption of the exchange sites on the B-IE-5.8 catalyst. On the contrary,
196 some Cu-ZSM5 catalysts exceed the 100 % exchange level, and this can be due either
197 to the formation of copper dimers in solution $(\text{Cu}^{2+}\text{OH}^-)_2$, which would result in the
198 anchoring of two Cu(II) ions per exchangeable site [19], and/or to the formation of
199 extraframework copper species. During the ion exchange, local changes in pH could
200 promote copper hydroxide precipitation [20].

201 In spite of this observation, the X ray diffractograms of the copper-exchanged
202 zeolites, which are not shown for the sake of brevity, did not present neither peaks
203 corresponding to metallic copper (Cu^0) nor to copper oxide (CuO), evidencing high
204 copper dispersion in all cases. Besides, the diffractograms of the acid and copper
205 exchanged zeolites are quite similar, which means that the crystalline structure of the
206 zeolites was not apparently modified after the copper incorporation.

207 Figure 2 shows the BET surface area of the catalysts as a function of the
208 copper loading. Fresh BETA and ZSM5 zeolites presented BET surface areas of 532
209 and $474 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, respectively. These areas decrease linearly, with almost the same
210 slope, with the copper content. This decrease of BET surface area can be attributed to
211 the partial pores blockage by copper species and/or to the destruction of micropores
212 during copper loading due to aluminum leaching by acid attack [21]. The surface area
213 decrease observed for the impregnated catalysts (B-IM-1.3 and Z-IM-1.2) are not in
214 line with their counterparts prepared by ion-exchange, and impregnated catalysts show

215 a much higher decrease in the BET surface area. This suggests that pore blockage by
216 copper species is the main reason of the BET surface area decrease.

217 **FIGURE 2**

218

219 *3.2 Analysis of the copper particle size by TEM.*

220 The copper particle size distributions on the different catalysts have been
221 determined by TEM. As an example, Figures 3a and 3b show TEM images of the
222 lowest and highest copper content ZSM5 catalysts, whereas Figures 3c and 3d show
223 the counterpart BETA catalysts, all of them prepared by ionic exchange.

224 **FIGURE 3**

225 As expected, the amount and size of the dark spots, mainly attributed to CuO as
226 it will be demonstrated afterwards, depends both on the nature of the zeolite and on the
227 copper loading. A major number of dark spots are observed for high-copper content
228 catalysts (Z-IE-4.9 and B-IE-5.8, Figures 3b and 3d) than for the counterpart low-
229 copper content catalysts, and BETA catalysts only shows small particles (diameter <
230 1.5 nm) while ZSM5 presents both small and large particles.

231 Figure 4 shows the copper particle size distribution for all catalysts. No relevant
232 differences were detected in the copper size distribution among catalysts prepared by
233 impregnation and ionic exchange.

234 **FIGURE 4**

235 As a general trend, BETA catalysts present narrower particle size distribution
236 than ZSM5 catalysts, with particle sizes centered on 1 nm and most particles being
237 smaller than 4 nm. Only the highest-copper content BETA catalyst (B-IE-5.8) shows
238 few copper particles larger than 10 nm. ZSM5 catalysts exhibit wider particle size

239 distributions than BETA catalysts, and a considerable amount of large particles,
240 especially for high copper loading catalyst, were identified. Few of these particles
241 achieved sizes even higher than 300 nm.

242 These observations are in good agreement with the conclusions of the previous
243 section, where it was observed that copper is mainly exchanged on zeolite sites of the
244 BETA support while an important fraction of the metal loaded on ZSM5 is impregnated
245 rather than exchanged (see Figure 1 and previous section).

246

247 *3.3 Analysis of the copper species nature by XPS and H₂-TPR.*

248 In order to study the surface composition of the catalysts and the nature of the
249 surface copper species, XPS characterization was carried out. A certain amount of
250 carbon was detected by XPS on the surface of all catalysts, close to 10% in some
251 cases, and for this reason a direct analysis of the quantitative results of the surface
252 composition is complex and comparison of elements ratio is more meaningful. This
253 carbon must be attributed to atmospheric CO₂ adsorption. In Table 2, the Si/Al surface
254 ratios are compiled together with the ratio between surface copper (determined by
255 XPS) and total copper (determined by ICP) contents.

256

TABLE 2

257 The Si/Al surface ratio decreases by increasing the copper loading both for
258 BETA and ZSM5 catalysts. This can be attributed to the decrease of the solutions pH
259 by increasing the Cu(II) precursor concentration, which favors the zeolites
260 dealumination [21]. This aluminum leaching would result in a certain accumulation of
261 aluminum species on the crystals surface.

262 The ratio between surface and total copper contents ($Cu_{\text{surface}}/Cu_{\text{total}}$) provides
263 information about the metal loading process. Constant ratios (0.42) were obtained for
264 BETA zeolite catalysts prepared by ionic exchange and a quite similar value was
265 obtained by impregnation of this support (0.37 for B-IM-1.3). These values below 1
266 indicate that copper is mainly accumulated into the zeolite porosity, and support that
267 copper cations are actually exchanged on the zeolite sites [22]. The similar values
268 obtained by the impregnation and ionic exchange loading methods suggest that copper
269 could be exchanged even in the impregnated BETA catalyst. For ZSM5 catalysts
270 prepared by ionic exchange, the $Cu_{\text{surface}}/Cu_{\text{total}}$ ratio increases with the copper loading
271 and most values are higher than those obtained with the counterpart BETA zeolite
272 catalysts. This is in line with the worst copper dispersion obtained on the ZSM5 zeolite
273 support. Note that higher particles were observed by TEM on ZSM5 zeolite catalysts
274 (see Figures 3 and 4). This worst dispersion of copper can be attributed to the lower
275 cation exchange capacity of the ZSM5 zeolite with regard to that of the BETA zeolite.
276 The $Cu_{\text{surface}}/Cu_{\text{total}}$ ratio obtained with the ZSM5 zeolite impregnated with copper (Z-IM-
277 1.2 catalyst) is higher than values obtained by ionic exchange of this zeolite, which is
278 an evidence of worst dispersion in this case.

279 Figures 5a and 5b show the X ray photoelectronic spectra corresponding to the
280 copper 2p transition for Cu-ZSM5 and Cu-BETA catalysts, respectively. It is usually
281 reported that $Cu(2p^{3/2})$ transition appears at energy values lower than 933 eV for
282 metallic copper (Cu^0) and Cu_2O ($Cu(I)$), while it shifts to values higher than 933 eV for
283 $Cu(II)$ species [23]. According to this assignation, all profiles included on Figure 5 are
284 consistent with the presence of different $Cu(II)$ species. The presence of the shake-up
285 satellite (not shown in Figure 5) appearing in all catalysts with energies 10 eV higher
286 than the $Cu(2p^{3/2})$ transition also gives evidences of the presence of $Cu(II)$. However,
287 the energy of the $Cu(2p^{3/2})$ transition does not allow unequivocally identify the oxidation

288 states of copper [21], and for the proper identification of the oxidation state of the
289 copper species the Auger peak must be taken into account. The Auger parameter (α),
290 which is calculated as the sum of copper 2p binding energy and Auger peak kinetic
291 energy, has been included in Table 3. The values of the Auger parameter of most
292 catalysts are well above 1850 eV, and these values confirm the presence of Cu(II)
293 cations. Only the Z-IE-4.9 catalyst presents Auger values below 1850 eV, and this
294 could be due to the formation of bulk CuO instead of Cu(II) cations exchanged on the
295 zeolite framework and/or to the presence of Cu(I) cations, but the formation of CuO
296 seems to be more reasonable [24].

297 TABLE 3

298 FIGURE 5

299 The Cu($2p^{3/2}$) transition included on Figure 5 can be deconvoluted in three main
300 contributions located around 933.2 eV, 934.0 eV and 936.0 eV. As discussed, all these
301 contributions can be most likely be attributed to different Cu(II) species [17]. The band
302 located at ca. 933.2 eV is tentatively assigned to agglomerated CuO particles present
303 on the surface [25], while second and third peaks located at ca. 934.0 and 936.0 eV
304 are thought to correspond to isolated Cu(II) species with different coordination, as was
305 evidenced by Hajjar et al. [26] by FTIR and MQMAS NMR. The peak at 934.0 eV
306 corresponds to isolated Cu(II) in tetrahedral coordination, while the peak appearing at
307 936.0 correspond to isolated Cu(II) in octahedral coordination [25], which is related to
308 the presence of two kinds of exchange sites in the zeolites framework. As isolated
309 Cu(II) in octahedral coordination are more strongly attached to the zeolite framework,
310 the corresponding contribution appears at the highest binding energy followed by
311 isolated Cu(II) in tetrahedral coordination and finally agglomerated Cu(II) species which
312 appear at the lowest binding energy.

313 The contribution of each individual transition to the total intensity of the $\text{Cu}(2p^{3/2})$
314 band depends both on the zeolite type and on the copper content. As a general trend,
315 increasing copper content leads to an increase in the contribution located at lowest
316 binding energy, i.e. 933.2 eV (dashed red line) to the detriment of that located at 934.0
317 eV (dashed green line), while the third one located at 936.0 eV (dashed blue line)
318 remains constant for Cu-ZSM5 and increases for Cu-BETA. The areas of these
319 contributions were calculated and expressed as a percentage of the total $\text{Cu}(2p^{3/2})$
320 transition in Table 3.

321 Note that the increasing contribution of the peak located at 933.2 eV, indicating
322 the presence of agglomerated CuO particles, increases with the copper loading: 13%
323 of the total $\text{Cu}(2p^{3/2})$ transition for Z-IE-1.4, 31 % for Z-IE-2.6 and 53 % for Z-IE-4.9.
324 Meanwhile, the contribution of isolated Cu(II) in tetrahedral coordination shows a
325 reverse relationship respect to the amount of agglomerated particles, decreasing with
326 increasing the copper content, i.e. 78 % for Z-IE-1.4, 59 % for Z-IE-2.6 and 38 % for Z-
327 IE-4.9. The contribution of isolated Cu(II) in octahedral coordination is almost
328 constant, around 9 %, regardless the copper loading. Thus, it can be suggested that
329 copper first preferentially occupies the ion exchange sites and, once those are
330 saturated, CuO is accumulated on the zeolite surface. Agglomerated CuO particles are
331 more abundant in ZSM5 zeolite than on BETA zeolite if catalysts with similar copper
332 loading are compared. For instance, the signal attributed to CuO particles represents
333 53 % in Z-IE-4.9 catalysts while it results in just 34 % for B-IE-5.8, although the copper
334 loading is even higher for the latter. This fact could be related to the lower ionic
335 exchange capacity of ZSM5, which promotes the formation of CuO aggregates for high
336 copper loadings. Finally, XPS does not show significant differences between ion
337 exchanged and impregnated samples, which reveals that the proportion of each copper
338 species on the surface is only influenced by the copper amount and the zeolite type.

339 Additional information about the nature of the different copper species in the
340 catalysts was obtained by Temperature Programmed Reduction experiments (H₂-TPR),
341 and Figure 6 shows the H₂ consumption profiles. The copper-free H-zeolites did not
342 contain reducible ions and no H₂ consumption was noticed; therefore, all H₂ consumed
343 by the catalysts can be attributed to the reduction of copper cations. It is important to
344 mention that the H₂-TPR profiles obtained with fresh catalysts (Figure 6) and after the
345 SCR experiments (not shown) did not show significant changes, confirming that copper
346 remains mainly oxidized even after the SCR experiments. This is not surprising taking
347 into account the highly oxidizing nature of the simulated diesel exhaust gas stream.

348 **FIGURE 6**

349 All the catalysts consumed H₂ due to the reduction of Cu(II), and the higher the
350 copper content of the catalysts, the higher the H₂ consumption [27]. Considering the
351 ICP-AES copper content, the amount of catalyst used in the H₂-TPR experiments and
352 the stoichiometry of the following reactions:

355 a H₂/Cu=1 ratio should be obtained if all copper were Cu(II) and if all Cu(II) species
356 were completely reduced to metal copper. According to the H₂/Cu ratios obtained
357 experimentally (0.9-1.0 in all cases), all the catalysts accomplish these hypotheses.
358 This confirms that only Cu(II) species exist on the catalysts, which is consistent with the
359 XPS results.

360 All the profiles included in Figure 6 are composed by several maxima and
361 shoulders indicating, in line with the XSP results, the presence of copper species with
362 different reducibility. The maximum that appears around 250 °C for most of the
363 catalysts corresponds to the reduction of bulk CuO species, which are more easily

364 reduced than exchanged Cu(II) ions [28]. A shoulder at lower temperatures, which is
365 related with the reduction of the CuO particles surface, is observed in some profiles,
366 and its contribution increases with the total copper content. The CuO reduction
367 maximum/shoulder observed in the H₂-TPR profiles would be associated to the copper
368 2p XPS contribution at 933.2 eV (see Figure 5 and Table 3).

369 The H₂-consumption peaks appearing at higher temperatures can be assigned
370 to Cu(II) cations exchanged on the zeolite, which need more temperature to be
371 reduced than CuO. The presence of different exchanged Cu(II) cations is consequence
372 of the existence of different kinds of framework sites in ZSM5 and BETA zeolites [26].
373 The peaks with a maximum at temperatures around 350 °C for ZSM5 catalysts and
374 around 450 °C for BETA catalyst, corresponds to the most easily reduced exchanged
375 Cu (II) species [28]. According to the XPS results, this peak could be related with the
376 reduction of tetraordinated Cu(II) species. Finally, the peaks with a maximum at
377 temperatures around 480 °C for ZSM5 catalysts and around 600 °C for BETA catalysts
378 correspond, in line with XPS results, to the reduction of Cu(II) cations in octahedral
379 coordination, which are strongly attached to the zeolite.

380 As it has been previously reported [27], there is a significant effect of copper
381 loading on the reducibility of the different copper species. From our data it can be
382 confirmed that an increase of the copper loading shifts the reduction peaks to lower
383 temperature. This is consistent with the formation of larger amounts of dimeric copper-
384 species as the copper loading increases [29]. These dimeric copper species contain
385 bridging oxygen atoms that can react with H₂ at comparably lower temperatures than
386 isolated copper-sites. Thus, as expected, the copper dispersion decreases for high
387 copper loading.

388 In addition to the qualitative assignation of the H₂-reduction peaks to the
389 different copper species in the catalyst, a semi-quantitative analysis of the H₂-
390 consumption profiles can be done. The highest temperature peaks (assigned to Cu(II)
391 cations exchanged on octahedral sites) are the most intense peaks for the low copper
392 content catalysts. This indicates that the octahedral sites are first exchanged. The
393 intensity of the peaks assigned to Cu(II) cations exchanged on tetrahedral sites grows
394 appreciably with the copper content, becoming more intense than the third contribution
395 (the one assigned to Cu(II) cations exchanged on octahedral sites). This confirms that
396 the tetra-coordinated sites are occupied by Cu(II) cations after the octahedral sites, and
397 that the amount of tetrahedral sites available on the zeolites is higher to that of
398 octahedral sites. Finally, the most intense H₂-reduction peak of the ZSM5 catalyst with
399 highest copper content (Z-IE-4.9) is assigned to CuO reduction, confirming that bulk
400 copper oxide formation is favored once the exchange sites have been occupied. On the
401 contrary, the position and intensity of the H₂-reduction peaks of B-IE-5.8 suggest that
402 Cu(II) exchanged on tetrahedral positions is the most abundant copper species on the
403 highest copper content BETA catalyst. This is consistent with the higher ionic exchange
404 capacity of the BETA zeolite with regard to that of the ZSM5 zeolite.

405 As a summary, the XPS and H₂-TPR characterization confirm the presence of
406 different Cu(II) species on the catalyst, namely, CuO and Cu(II) exchanged on
407 tetrahedral and octahedral positions of the zeolite framework. Clear evidences of Cu(I)
408 or Cu(0) species were not obtained in any case. As a general trend, Cu(II) exchanged
409 on octahedral positions prevails for catalysts with low copper content, and the
410 exchange of Cu(II) on tetrahedral positions and the formation of CuO is progressively
411 favored by increasing the copper content. The formation of CuO is more important on
412 the ZSM5 zeolite than on BETA due to the lower ionic exchange capacity of the former.

413

414 3.4. SCR experiments.

415 Figures 7a and 7b show the NO_x and NH₃ conversions and Figures 7c, 7d and
416 7e show the selectivity towards N₂, NO₂ and N₂O, respectively, as a function of the
417 reaction temperature in SCR experiments.

418 FIGURE 7

419 The behavior of any catalyst is qualitatively similar, and the obtained catalytic
420 results are typical of NO_x SCR reactions in all cases. NO conversions increased with
421 temperature because the NH₃-NO_x reactions are promoted, reaching a maximum
422 conversion for an intermediate temperature and decreasing afterwards as the oxidation
423 of ammonia with O₂ is favored at high temperature [30, 31]. The NH₃ conversions also
424 increased with temperature, but 100% conversion was maintained above a certain
425 temperature because the NH₃-O₂ reaction prevails. The minimum temperature for
426 100% ammonia conversion is the same at which the maximum NO conversion is
427 achieved. Regardless the catalyst, N₂ is the main nitrogen-reaction product (above
428 80% selectivity in the whole range of temperatures studied for all catalyst) and few N₂O
429 and/or NO₂ are only detected.

430 The particular behavior of the catalysts depends both on the zeolite nature and
431 the copper loading. For catalysts prepared with the same zeolite, the NO and NH₃
432 conversion curves are shifted to lower temperatures as the copper content increases,
433 while the N₂O and NO₂ selectivities slightly increase. As discussed in the previous
434 characterization sections, the presence of CuO is favored for high copper contents, and
435 this would explain these catalytic trends. A tentative explanation is that CuO catalyzes
436 the oxidation of NO to NO₂, and this favors the reduction of NO_x at lower temperature
437 since the NH₃-NO₂ reaction is faster than the NH₃-NO reaction (NO₂ is much more
438 oxidizing than NO). The formation of NO₂ is only evident at high temperature, once the

439 selectivity of the $\text{NH}_3\text{-NO}_x$ reactions decrease, because in the range of temperatures of
440 high NO reduction selectivity the NO_2 potentially formed is expected to react with NH_3 ,
441 and consequently, is not detected.

442 The low-copper content catalysts, and mainly those prepared by ionic exchange
443 and with BETA zeolite, have a better catalytic behavior at high temperature than the
444 high-copper content counterparts. For instance, at 425 °C, the catalyst B-IE-2.1
445 reached the highest NO conversion among all catalysts, keeping low NO_2 and N_2O
446 production. This catalyst has a high proportion of exchanged Cu(II) species (mainly
447 Cu(II) exchanged on octahedral sites), and this type of copper cations seems to be
448 responsible of the activity at high temperature. It can be concluded that CuO clusters,
449 which are more abundant in high copper-content catalysts, promote NO reduction at
450 low temperature whereas isolated Cu(II) ions, which are more abundant in low copper-
451 content catalysts, maintained high NO_x conversion even at high temperatures. In
452 addition, catalysts with low CuO content exhibit higher N_2 selectivity, which was
453 progressively reduced by increasing the copper loading. In those cases, the selectivity
454 of the reaction moved towards N_2O and NO_2 .

455 Comparing the supports, it can be observed that Cu-ZSM5 catalysts are more
456 active at low temperature whereas Cu-BETA catalysts maintain higher activity at high
457 temperature. This behavior can also be related to the nature of the copper species
458 present in each catalyst. As a general trend, there are higher amounts of CuO on
459 ZSM5 catalysts than on BETA catalysts due to the lower ionic exchange capacity of the
460 ZSM5 zeolite.

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463

464 **4. Conclusions.**

465 In this study, the SCR of NO_x with NH₃ has been studied with different copper
466 zeolite catalysts and the following conclusions have been achieved:

467 The catalysts characterization confirmed the presence of different Cu(II) species
468 in all catalyst, namely, CuO and Cu(II) exchanged on tetrahedral and octahedral
469 positions of the zeolite framework. Clear evidences of Cu(I) or Cu(0) species were not
470 obtained in any case. As a general trend, Cu(II) exchanged on octahedral positions
471 prevails for catalysts with low copper content, and the exchange of Cu(II) on tetrahedral
472 positions and the formation of CuO is progressively favored by increasing the copper
473 content.

474 CuO is more abundant in high copper-content catalysts and in ZSM5 catalysts,
475 while isolated Cu(II) ions are more abundant in low copper-content catalysts and in
476 BETA catalysts. There are higher amounts of CuO on ZSM5 catalysts than on BETA
477 catalysts due to the lower ionic exchange capacity of the ZSM5 zeolite.

478 The nature of the copper species affects the SCR behavior of the studied
479 catalysts. CuO clusters promote NO reduction at low temperature whereas isolated
480 Cu(II) ions maintain high NO_x conversion at high temperatures. In addition, catalysts
481 with low CuO content exhibit higher N₂ selectivity, since CuO promotes the formation of
482 N₂O and NO₂.

483 It is suggested that CuO catalyzes the oxidation of NO to NO₂, and this favors
484 the reduction of NO_x at lower temperature since the NH₃-NO₂ reaction is faster than the
485 NH₃-NO reaction (NO₂ is much more oxidizing than NO).

486

487

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493

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- 589

590 **Figure Captions.**

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592

593 **Figure 1.** Relation between the initial copper concentration and the actual copper
594 content (%) in zeolite.

595

596 **Figure 2.** Relation between the actual copper content and BET surface area.

597

598 **Figure 3.** TEM images of (a) Z-IE-1.4, (b) Z-IE-4.9, (c) B-IE-2.1 and (d) B-IE-5.8.

599

600 **Figure 4.** Particle size distribution of catalysts determined from TEM images.

601

602 **Figure 5.** X ray Photoelectric Spectra (copper $2p^{3/2}$ transition) for (a) Cu-ZSM5
603 catalysts and (b) Cu-BETA catalysts.

604

605 **Figure 6.** H_2 -TPR profiles of fresh: a) Cu-BETA catalysts and (b) Cu-ZSM-5 catalysts.

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607 **Figure 7.** Conversion of NO_x , NH_3 and N_2 , N_2O and NO_2 selectivity during SCR
608 reaction for (a) BETA and (b) ZSM5 catalysts.

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Table 1. Summary of the prepared catalysts

Catalyst nomenclature	Support	Si/Al	Copper loading method	Copper initial concentration in the impregnation solutions (ppm)	Copper content on the catalyst (wt. %)	Exchange sites potentially* occupied by Cu(II) cations (%)
B-IM-1.3	BETA	12.5	Impregnation	-	1.3	23
B-IE-2.1	BETA	12.5	Ion exchange	320	2.1	37
B-IE-2.9	BETA	12.5	Ion exchange	640	2.9	52
B-IE-5.8	BETA	12.5	Ion exchange	2000	5.8	103
Z-IM-1.2	ZSM5	25	Impregnation	-	1.2	59
Z-IE-1.4	ZSM5	25	Ion exchange	160	1.4	69
Z-IE-2.6	ZSM5	25	Ion exchange	640	2.6	129
Z-IE-4.9	ZSM5	25	Ion exchange	2000	4.9	243

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Table 2. Results of the surface characterization by XPS.

Catalyst	Cu _{surface} /Cu _{total}	Si/Al
Z-IM-1.2	0.78	14
Z-IE-1.4	0.38	14
Z-IE-2.6	0.58	8
Z-IE-4.9	0.64	5
B-IM-1.3	0.37	11
B-IE-2.1	0.42	8
B-IE-2.9	0.42	7
B-IE-5.8	0.42	6

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617

618 **Table 3.** XPS characterization of the copper species. Percentage of the different
 619 copper species identified in the Cu2p^{3/2} transition and Auger energy.

Catalyst	Peak at 933.2 eV (%)	Peak at 934.0 eV (%)	Peak at 936.0 eV (%)	Auger (eV)
Z-IM-1.2	9	83	8	1865.3
Z-IE-1.4	13	78	8	1865.6
Z-IE-2.6	31	59	10	1865.2
Z-IE-4.9	53	38	9	1848.6
B-IM-1.3	9	79	12	1865.6
B-IE-2.1	16	74	10	1865.5
B-IE-2.9	27	57	16	1865.9
B-IE-5.8	34	45	21	1862.3

620 Tentative assignment: 933.2 eV corresponds to CuO, 934.0 eV corresponds to isolated Cu(II) in
 621 tetrahedral coordination and 936.0 eV corresponds to isolated Cu(II) in octahedral
 622 coordination (see main text for details).

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

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Figure 5

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Figure 6

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Figure 7